

UNVEILLING THE HIDDEN DIMENSIONS OF WORKPLACE BULLYING: A STUDY ON CAUSES AND SEQUENCES

Seemab Abid^{*1}, Noreen Shakoor²

^{*1}Lecturer Sociology Department

²Senior Teacher Assistant Sociology Department, SBK women's University, Quetta, Baluchistan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16750926>

Keywords

Workplace bullying, work performance, academic workers

Article History

Received on 06 May 2025

Accepted on 20 July 2025

Published on 06 August 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Seemab Abid

Abstract

Work place bullying is related to many socio-psychological and professional issues. Study identify that workers who undergo bullying style of working environment tend to react with negative workplace attitudes and behaviors. However, the mechanisms that can explain this relationship must be identified in order to understand this phenomenon. In this connection nature of workplace bullying and types of bullying is attempted to examine through this study. Following research also through light different types of bullying behavior that directly and indirectly affects professional health of female workers. . Mixed method research approach is used to obtain the data. Data will obtain from 30% female academic worker of 8 different higher educational institutions of Baluchistan. Semi-structured questionnaire were use from Target respondents for collecting data. Statistical tools are used for analyzing numerical data and qualitative data is analyzed through thematic analysis. Theoretical and practical implications are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

As an imperative area of debate on the concept of Workplace bullying is increasingly recognized, particularly wide range of definitions and conception regarding this phenomenon was used to define its real concept (Hutchinson, Vickers, Jackson & Wilkes, 2010).

Many key terms from which English-speaking countries are imply to explained the bullying phenomenon like the countries like German were the use word mobbing instead of bullying. All the definitions, explained similar issues like a biased behavior against others, aggressor towards the victim, destructive, systematized and consistent action. The sufferers in this situation feel inferior and begin experiencing the helpless in this situation.

Rosenthal (2008) & Oade, (2009) explain in their study, that bullying is the individual's aggressive

and unwanted behavior against others. In this situations Person are involve aggressive behavior that force others to do something.

Bullying behavior can be notice in various forms, but the bullying at workplace is one of the most complex types of bullying and it can be is defined as health harming act of a person and repeated mistreatment against others (Cappellaro, 2017). Salin, (2003) define that workplace bullying as issue of utmost importance. This issue cannot be ignored because it is one of the most costly problems. Many studies have been published on the issue of work place bullying and that aims to address issues cause by workplace bullying such as, the suffering, physical illness, role strain, and disappointment among employees. (Stainton, 2018).

Simply, the workplace bullying improper, intolerable behavior, which have adversely affects the worker's self-esteem. The main cause of this type of disgraced behavior against others consider the other person substandard in place of work (Lohikoski.et.al.,2019).

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

In this study researcher not only try to explain the concept of workplace bullying but also highlight various type of non-professional behavior that are identify as workplace bullying that ultimately effect not only the productivity and job performance but also overall personality of employee.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To determine the root causes of work place bullying that effect female academic workers of higher education institutions.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTION:

The aim of the study to identify and pointed out all types of non-professional and work place bullying behaviors that are faced by female academic workers in higher educational institutions

1.4 HYPOTHESIS:

H1: Employee Macrosystem as Non- professional behavior of employees is significant for workplace bullying against female academic workers of higher educational institutions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to researchers, work place bullying is uncommonly indicated physical hostility that is result of invoke negative interpretations at workplace. For example, term bullying is widely used in UK (Leymann, 1996., Samnani & Singh, 2012). US word bullying is explained as abusive supervision (Tepper, 2000), countries like Germany and Europe (Einarsen, 2011) mobbing is used to explained behaviors like emotional abuse (Harvey& Keashly, 2005) harassment and aggressiveness at the workplace (Brodsky, 1976). Whereas in different studies different definitions and terms are used to explained the really

phenomena of workplace bullying but researchers are common agreed on operationalized bullying, and defined as a condition in more persons is continuously and repeatedly involved in to negative acts against an individual. There are normally numbers of factors involved due to which people feel them helpless to protect themselves against such behavior and imbalance power (Einarsen, 2000; Hoel, Vartia, 2003; Salin, 2003; Einarsen et al., 2011; Zapf, Einarsen, Park and Ono,2017) and authority is considered as of the big reason of work place bullying((Einarsen et al., 2011)

Einarsen and Hoel (2001) conducting study based on compression between of work-oriented bullying and individually directed bullying by using NAQ's (Negative Acts Questionnaire) confirmatory factor analysis. He further explained that personal bullying is include all the negative behaviors against other to do personal attacks such as humiliating, gossiping, criticizing and making fun of them(Copper & Faragher, 2011). On the other hand, individual directed bullying behaviors is always target one's work like, increase workloads, trouncing importance, strict monitoring and sets unrealistic deadlines and hiding importance information from the victim. (Einarsen & Hoel, 2001). At Every workplace directly and indirectly many people are involved in workplace bullying. In Workplace setting these gangs and people can be observed while supporting bully for some mutual benefits. These gangs cause disasters in organizations (Wankhade & Kamble, 2018; Rofcanin et al., 2017).

Past investigation prof that many type of workplace bullying is existing in workplace environment such as aggressive and abusive behavior. In many countries the act of bullying is not acceptable, but despite of this issue of workplace bullying is commonly prevailing not only in developed countries but also in developing countries. (Olweus, 1999; Mathisen, Einarsen & Mykletun, 2008).

3. MATHODOLOGY

Sami-structured or mixed questionnaire was used; **Mixed Questionnaires** consist of close-formatted questions as well as open-ended

questions. For analysis of the quantitative part of the study statistical tools correlation and co-variance is used, for qualitative analysis is used to analyze the data in order to draw findings.

3.1 DATA COLLCECTION:

In this research units of analysis were female’s academic workers of higher education institutions

3.3 THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Ecological Model

Phenomena of workplace bullying can be illustrated with the help of the ecological perspective which is based on ecological perspective which is based on ecological conceptual model. The ecological model depicts that in society, the work environment as a whole consists of a series of interconnected and nested layers. These layers are named **macro-system** means society, **eco-system** refers to the corporation and the last one is **meso-system** means target. Workplace setting bully and the target is belonging to the microsystem. The ecological perspective portrays that the workplace can’t be taken place in isolation. The layers of each level contain elements that work as antecedents to bullying and at each of these levels bullying outcomes are manifested. The model of ecological perspective can also facilitate empirical research in the formulation of questions (Johnson, 2011).

The Individual Employee

The center of this model is an individual employee. The personal biography of an employee

in Quetta city of Baluchistan. Data will obtain from 268 female academic workers of 7 different higher educational institutions of Baluchistan that is 30% of the total population.

3.2 DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical tool I.e., chi-square and analysis of variance is used to analysis the data.

indicates that environmental settings such as, culture, community, home and even workplace are influenced the employee to the great extent. These locales affect the employee; as a result relationship between the outer layer of the paradigm and the employee is become reciprocal with each other (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). In this way, the environment influenced the employee as much as the employee impacts their environment.

Employee Exo-system

The exo-system denotes a type of setting in which events occur in the setting containing” the employee and play an active role that ultimately affects, or are affected the employee but the employee is not involved as an active participant (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). In Australia, to workplace issues multiple policies and organizations dedicated. Many of them are focusing on the safety, health, and well-being of employees and “an unprecedented public policy has witnessed an emphasis on promoting good health and the preventing ill health from the last decade ” (Murray, al, el, 2013). The exo-system refers to employee well-being in terms of the “protective” domain (Ball and Trembath, 2013).

3.4 ANALYSIS:

Employee Macro-system as Non- professional behavior of employees is significant for workplace bullying against female academic workers of higher educational institutions.

Table 1.1

S#	Independent Variable	S#	Dependent Variable(WPBS 1992)
NPB1	Friendship offers	WPBS1	Gazing
NPB2	Undue favors	WPBS2	Unfair treatment
NPB3	Black-mailing	WPBS3	Touching
NPB4	Unnecessary calls	WPBS4	Threatening behavior

NPB5	Unnecessary visits to the room	WPBS5	Bursting malicious humors/jokes
NPB6	Unnecessary rude behavior	WPBS6	Giving sexual gestures
NPB7	Demotivating	WPBS7	Discriminating
NPB8	Over burdening		
NP9	Creating barriers in promotional opportunities		
	Alpha value =0.828		Alpha value= 0.660

*NPB= Non-professional Behavior

*WPBS= workplace Bullying Scale

Hypothesis 1B Independent Variable
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.828	9

Hypothesis 1B Dependent Variable
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.660	6

Hypothesis 1B

Correlations

		H1_Dep
H1_ind	Pearson Correlation	.674**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Covariance	.551
	N	266

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Note: Correlation result indicates there is a moderate level of positive relationship among both variables (0.674). Also this relationship is significant because it is less than 5%.

3.5 Results:

A Self-administrated scale was used by the researcher to evaluate the relation between nonprofessional behavior and workplace bullying for this purpose five points Likert scale is used to take the response of the respondents. to identify the nature of the both variable nonprofessional behavior and workplace bullying at the workplace both visible and invisible factors are

utilized. Table 1.1 shows that the non-professional behavior of the supervisor is significant for encouraging workplace bullying against female workers of higher educational institutions, as the results indicate That $R=0.67$, ($p=0.00$). Results show that the majority of the respondents (42.8%) respond that they are never having Friendship offers in the workplace. (49%) mostly respondents never

entertained by Undue favors. (44.6%) respondent is not facing Blackmailing in their working environment. (53.2%) respond shows that they are not facing problems of unnecessary calls by their colleagues or supervisor (63.9%) respondents never face unnecessary visits to their room of any unwanted person in their workplace. The Majority of the respondent (32.3%) respond that often they are facing Unnecessary rude behavior in their workplace. Most responses (27.5%) indicate, they are being demotivating in their working environment. (28.6%) respond that they are often Over burdening by official tasks. (39.8%) responses show that often people in their organization creating barriers in promotional opportunities. As results indicate that people in workplace have non-professional behavior in term of unnecessary rude behavior, and creating barriers in promotional opportunities, demotivating, overburdening are normal behavior. This type of nonprofessional behavior plays a significant role in facilitating workplace bullying, as percentages of the results WB1 (27.1%), WB2 (35.3%), WB7 (32.3%) affirmed it.

CONCLUSION:

Non-professional attitude of the people are significantly associated with workplace bullying. The significant value is less than .001 and model is moderate. Results indicate that relationship is significant. Numerous studies discusses that the

consequences of various workplace negative behavior and abusive supervision result into employee's counterproductive behavior (Tepper, 2000, 2007, 2011, 2014).

Responses of respondent also pinpoint different other negative behavior at workplace that's effects their work performances. As Zapf & Copper(2011) explained that bullying is include all the negative behaviors such as making fun of other, criticizing , gossiping, against other, and humiliating other in order to do personal attacks (Zapf & Copper, 2011). Some of them are also victims individual in directed bullying behaviors. Workplace environment is another associated with workplace bullying.

The study on bullying behavior and workplace bullying environment is still in initial stages, in order to get a lucid picture of workplace bullying organization needs more intensive researches on different lines must be conducted. To contribute abusive supervision there is huge need to identify the feature of the study. The overall assumption is concluded on the basis of the findings and the results of the study is that workplace bullying environment and bullying behavior has a drastic impact of workplace bullying and work performance of female academic workers. Furthermore, the research attempts to confirm that the workplace bullying is highly associated with overall wellbeing of workers employees. (Nielsen & Einarsen, 2012; Samnani & Singh, 2012; Tuckey & Neall, 2014).

REFERANCES:

- Bronfenbrenner, U.** (1977). Toward an experimental ecology of human development. *American psychologist*, 32 (7), 513.
- Bronfenbrenner, U.** (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design.* Harvard University Press
- Cooper Thomas, H., Gardner, D., O'Driscoll, M., Catley, B., Bentley, T., & Trenberth, L.** (2013). Neutralizing workplace bullying: The buffering effects of contextual factors. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 28(4), 384-407.
- Gina, J.,**(2020). *Strategies to reduce workplace bullying in the pharmaceutical industry.* Walden University.
- Eisenberger, Robert, Huntington, Robin, Hutchison, Steven, Sowa,** *Perceived organizational support.* Debora, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol 71(3), Aug 1986, 500-507

- Elfi Baillien, I. N.** (2006). A Qualitative Study on the Development of Workplace Bullying: Towards a Three Way Model. *Wiley Online Dictionary*.
- Espelage, D.L., Berry, B., Merrin, J., & Swearer, S.M.** (2014). Social-ecological model for predicting workplace bullying. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257306560>
- Karatuna, I.**(2015) Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management: An International Journal Article information.
- Karriker, J. & Williams, M.** (2007). Organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior: A mediated multifocal model. *Journal Of Management*, 35(1), 112-135.
- Tashakkori, A., & Cresswell.** (2007). The new era of mixed methods. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Tepper, B., Moss, S., & Duffy, M.** (2011). Predictors of Abusive Supervision: Supervisor Perceptions of Deep-Level Dissimilarity, Relationship Conflict, and Subordinate Performance. *Academy Of Management Journal*, 54(2), 279-294.
- Tomprou, M., Nikolaou, I., & Vakola, M.** (2012). Experiencing organizational change in Greece: the framework of psychological contract. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(2), 385-405.
- Tepper, B., Moss, S., & Duffy, M.** (2011). Predictors of Abusive Supervision: Supervisor Perceptions of Deep-Level Dissimilarity, Relationship Conflict, and Subordinate Performance. *Academy Of Management Journal*, 54(2), 279-294.
- Thau Benett, Mitchell, Marrs** (2009). How Management style moderates the relationship between abusive supervision and workplace deviance: An Uncertainty Management theory perspective. *Organization behavior and Human decision process*, 108(1), 79-92.
- Tepper, B., Moss, S., Lockhart, D., & Carr, J.** (2007). Abusive supervision, upward maintenance communication, and subordinates' psychological distress. *Academy Of Management Journal*, 50(5), 1169-1180.
- Tepper, B., Duffy, M., & Hoobler** (2004). Moderators of the relationship between coworkers organizational citizenship behavior and employee attitude, *The Journal of Applied Psychology* 89(3), 455-465.
- Zellars, K. L., Tepper, B. J., & Duffy, M. K.** (2002). Abusive supervision and subordinates' organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 87(6), 1068-1076.
- Zhao, X., Lynch, J. G., & Chen, Q.** (2010). Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and truths about mediation analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37, 197-206.
- Zhou, Q., Hirst, G., & Shipton, H.** (2012). Promoting creativity at work: The role of problem-solving demand. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 61, 56-80.